

SURFACE INTEGRALS IN MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

**Methodology of teaching exact and natural sciences (Mathematics) 2nd year
master's degree**

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Abstract: In this article, methods of working examples related to the calculation of surface integrals of the first type and some applications of surface integrals, that is, finding the mass of several bodies, are considered, and a convenient method of teaching them to students of higher education institutions is analyzed.

Key words: integrals, surface integrals, surface integrals of the first type, multiple integrals, surface integral applications.

MATEMATIK ANALIZ FANIDA SIRT INTEGRALLARI

Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti

*Aniq va tabiiy fanlarni o'qitish metodikasi (Matematika) yo'nalishi 2-kurs
magistiri*

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada birinchi tur sirt integrallarni hisoblash va sirt integrallarning baʼzi tadbiqlariga doir, yaʼni bir nechta jismlarning massasini topishga oid misollarning ishlanish usullari koʻrib chiqilgan va oliy taʼlim muassasalari talabalariga oʻrgatishning qulay metodikasi tahlil qilingan.

Kalit soʻzlar: *integrallar, sirt integrallar, birinchi tur sirt integrallar, karrali integrallar, sirt integral tadbiqlari.*

Faraz qilaylik, R^3 fazoda (S) sirt $z = z(x, y)$ tenglama bilan berilgan bo'lib, $z(x, y)$ funksiya chegaralangan (D) sohada uzluksiz va (D) da uzluksiz (z_x, z_y) hosilalarga ega bo'lsin[1].

1-teorema. Agar $f(x, y, z)$ funksiya (S) sirtida berilgan va uzluksiz bo'lsa, u holda bu funksiyaning (S) sirt bo'yicha birinchi tur sirt integrali

$$\iint_{(S)} f(x, y, z) ds$$

Mavjud va

$$\iint_{(S)} f(x, y, z) ds = \iint_{(D)} f(x, y, z(x, y)) \sqrt{1 + (z'_x)^2 + (z'_y)^2} dx dy \quad (1)$$

bo'ladi.

Birinchi tur sirt integralining ba'zi tadbirlari. Birinchi tur sirt integrallaridan sirtning yuzini, massani hisoblashda, og'irlik markazining koordinatlarini hamda inersiya momentlarini topishda ham foydalaniladi[1,2].

1. (S) sirtning yuzi

$$S = \iint_{(S)} ds \quad (2)$$

formula yordamida topiladi.

2. Agar (S) sirt bo'yicha zichligi bo'lgan massa tarqatilgan bo'lsa, unda (S) sirtning massasi $m = \iint_{(S)} p(x, y, z) ds$

$$m = \iint_{(S)} p(x, y, z) ds \quad (3)$$

1-misol. Ushbu $\iint_{(S)} x ds$ integralni hisoblang, bunda (S) sirt quyidagi $z = \sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}$ yarim sferadan iborat[2].

Yechilishi.

1-rasm

Qaralayotgan S soha tenglama $z = \sqrt{1 - x^2 + y^2}$ bilan ifodalanadi (1-rasm). Bunda $z = z(x, y)$ funksiya $D = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : x^2 + y^2 \leq 1\}$ uzluksiz hamda uzluksiz xususiy hosilalarga ega:

$$z'_x = \frac{-x}{\sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}} \quad z'_y = \frac{-y}{\sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}}$$

Bu D soha $z = \sqrt{1 - x^2 + y^2}$ sirtning XOY tekislikdagi proyeksiyasi. Quyidagi birinchi tur sirt integralni berilgan (1) formula yordamida hisoblaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \iint_{(S)} x ds = \iint_{(D)} x \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{y}{\sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}}\right)^2} dx dy = \int_{-1}^1 dy \int_{-\sqrt{1-y^2}}^{\sqrt{1-y^2}} \frac{x}{\sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}} dx = \\ &= \int_{-1}^1 \left(\int_{-\sqrt{1-y^2}}^0 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}} dx + \int_0^{\sqrt{1-y^2}} \frac{x}{\sqrt{1 - x^2 - y^2}} dx \right) dy = \int_{-1}^1 -\sqrt{1 - y^2} dy + \int_{-1}^1 \sqrt{1 - y^2} dy = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Javob: 0

Sirt integrallarni hisoblash va sirt integrallarning ba'zi tadbirlarini misollar yordamida o'rganish orqali matematika fanini boshqa fanlardagi tutgan o'rnini ham ko'rsatish mumkin. Masalan, ushbu maqolada ko'rib chiqilgan birinchi tur

sirt integrallar yordamida jismlar massasini hisoblashga oid misollar nafaqat matematika fanida, balki fizika, kimyo va shu bilan birga texnikaning bir qator muammolarini hal qilishda ham uchrab turadi. Shulardan kelib chiqqan holda ushbu mavzu to'la yoritib berilishi orqali oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining fanga bo'lgan qiziqishi, mantiqiy fikrlashi va muammoni kreativ yondashuv yo'li bilan hal qilish ko'nikmasini shakllantiriladi.

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